

POST-BUCKLING OF DYNAMICALLY LOADED COMPOSITE PANELS USING A REDUCED ORDER MODEL

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Abstract

The present work is concerned with the buckling and post-buckling behavior of structures under dynamic loading, such as step loading or impulsive loading. Objective of the work is the application of a reduced order approach for the post-buckling analysis of structures with stable post-buckling behavior, such as stiffened panels, under dynamic loading. A multi-mode reduced order formulation is presented. Typical results for a single-mode reduced order post-buckling analysis under dynamic loading are shown for a composite stiffened panel under step loading.

1 Introduction

Thin-walled structures are prone to buckling instabilities under static and dynamic compressive loading. The present work is concerned with the buckling and post-buckling behavior of structures under dynamic loading, such as step loading or impulsive loading. Here one can distinguish between the behavior of imperfection-sensitive structures and the behavior of structures with stable (static) post-buckling behavior. The possibility to carry out a nonlinear transient analysis for thin-walled structures is standardly available within Finite Element (FE) codes. However, FE based transient analysis is computationally expensive and not suitable for the repeated runs necessary for a design and optimization process, and often it is difficult to interpret the result and to judge its correctness. Reduced order models (reduction methods) for general transient analysis of structures have therefore received considerable attention in recent years [1-4]. In recent work [5], a reduced order approach for dynamic stability analysis of general structures within an FE framework has been presented, in particular with an eye on imperfection-sensitive structures. The reduction method proposed makes use of a perturbation approach for nonlinear

static buckling analysis (Koiter's approach) and its extension to dynamic buckling analysis using Budiansky's approach [6]. The method has been applied by the present authors in their earlier work to dynamic buckling of composite cylindrical shells under step loading. Single-mode dynamic buckling analysis was carried out for unstiffened and ring-stiffened composite cylindrical shells. It has been shown that in these specific cases the approach gives reasonable estimates of the dynamic buckling load under step loading [5].

Objective of the present work is the application of the reduced order approach developed earlier in [5], in the buckling and post-buckling analysis of structures with stable post-buckling behavior, such as stiffened panels, under dynamic loading. The extension of the approach from [5] to a multi-mode formulation is presented. Typical results for a single-mode reduced order post-buckling analysis under dynamic loading are shown for a composite stiffened panel under step loading.

2 Perturbation Method

In the present work the earlier implementation of a perturbation approach for static and dynamic buckling analysis presented by Rahman and Jansen [7] and Rahman et al. [1] will be briefly recapitulated. The extension to account for inertial forces in order to be able to analyse dynamic buckling problems was done along the lines proposed by Budiansky [6]. For clarity and conciseness, the approach will be presented for a linear pre-buckling state, and the modifications necessary in order to include a nonlinear pre-buckling state will be inserted in the final equations.

Using a functional notation, and introducing the generalized displacement \mathbf{u} , strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, load \mathbf{f} , and stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, it is assumed that the nonlinear strain-

displacement relation and the linear elastic constitutive relation of a structure can be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = L_1(\mathbf{u}) + \frac{1}{2}L_2(\mathbf{u}) \quad (1)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = H(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \quad (2)$$

where L_1 and H are linear functionals and L_2 is a quadratic functional. The equilibrium equation in variational form is written as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{f} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Here $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and $\mathbf{f} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u}$ denote, respectively, the internal virtual work of the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ through the strain variation $\delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, and the external virtual work of the load \mathbf{f} through the displacement variation $\delta \mathbf{u}$, both integrated over the entire structure. Further, if the bilinear functional L_{11} is defined such that

$$L_2(\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}) = L_2(\mathbf{u}) + 2L_{11}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) + L_2(\mathbf{v}) \quad (4)$$

then it follows from (1) that the first order strain variation $\delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ produced by $\delta \mathbf{u}$ can be written as

$$\delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = L_1(\delta \mathbf{u}) + L_{11}(\mathbf{u}, \delta \mathbf{u}) \quad (5)$$

It will also be assumed that the reciprocity relation

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_j = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_j \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \quad (i, j = 1, 2, \dots) \quad (6)$$

holds.

In this study proportional loading will be considered, i.e. $\mathbf{f} = \lambda \mathbf{f}_0$, where λ is a normalized load parameter. Now the variables $(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\sigma})$ of the post-buckling equilibrium state can be expanded in the following perturbation series,

$$\mathbf{u} = \lambda \mathbf{u}_0 + \mathbf{u}_1 \xi + \mathbf{u}_2 \xi^2 + \mathbf{u}_3 \xi^3 + \dots \quad (7)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \lambda \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0 + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 \xi + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 \xi^2 + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_3 \xi^3 + \dots \quad (8)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \lambda \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 \xi + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 \xi^2 + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_3 \xi^3 + \dots \quad (9)$$

where ξ is a normalized mode amplitude. The perturbation expansions in Equation (7) are assumed to be asymptotically valid in the neighborhood of the pre-buckling equilibrium state corresponding to a bifurcation buckling load $\lambda = \lambda_c$. In the following it will be assumed that this buckling load corresponds to the lowest buckling load. Substituting Equations

(7) into Equations (1), (2) and (3), taking the limit $\xi \rightarrow 0$, and with some further manipulations one obtains the equations for the (lowest) buckling load λ_c and the corresponding buckling mode \mathbf{u}_1 ,

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 = L_1(\mathbf{u}_1) \quad (10)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 = H(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1) \quad (11)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 \cdot L_{11}(\delta \mathbf{u}) + \lambda_c \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 \cdot L_{11}(\mathbf{u}_1, \delta \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (12)$$

Assuming that the pre-buckling solution is linear the following relation holds,

$$L_{11}(\mathbf{u}_0, \delta \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (13)$$

In addition, it will be assumed that $(\lambda - \lambda_c)$ admits the asymptotic perturbation expansion

$$\lambda - \lambda_c = a \lambda_c \xi + b \lambda_c \xi^2 + \dots \quad (14)$$

If a plot of load parameter λ versus the mode amplitude ξ is made, then in view of Equation (14) the a and b coefficients indicate the slope and curvature of the post-buckling curve, respectively. If a "symmetric" structure is considered, the post-buckling slope is equal to zero, $a=0$, and in that case, the post-buckling coefficient b indicates whether the structure is imperfection-sensitive ($b < 0$) or not. Inserting Equation (14) together with Equation (7) into Equations (1), (2), and (3), and equating the coefficients of ξ^2 , for the case that $a=0$ ("symmetric" structures), one obtains the equations for the determination of the second order mode \mathbf{u}_2 ,

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 = L_1(\mathbf{u}_2) + \frac{1}{2}L_2(\mathbf{u}_1) \quad (15)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 = H(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2) \quad (16)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_2 \cdot L_{11}(\delta \mathbf{u}) + \lambda_c \boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 \cdot L_{11}(\mathbf{u}_2, \delta \mathbf{u}) + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_1 \cdot L_{11}(\mathbf{u}_1, \delta \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (17)$$

For the second order mode \mathbf{u}_2 , the following orthogonality condition is imposed,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0 \cdot L_{11}(\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2) = 0 \quad (18)$$

In order to obtain the expression for the b coefficient we set $\delta\mathbf{u}=\mathbf{u}_1$ in Equations (12) and (17) and make use of the reciprocity relation (6). This gives

$$b = \frac{2\sigma_1 \cdot L_{11}(\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2) + \sigma_2 \cdot L_2(\mathbf{u}_1)}{\sigma_1 \cdot \varepsilon_1} \quad (19)$$

Next, the behavior of the imperfect structure will be related to the properties of the perfect structure. If the initial geometric imperfection is denoted by $\xi^* \mathbf{u}_1$, where ξ^* is the normalized imperfection amplitude and \mathbf{u}_1 is a geometric imperfection pattern in the shape of the first buckling mode, then the strain-displacement equation, Equation (1), can be modified to

$$\varepsilon = L_1(\mathbf{u}) + \frac{1}{2}L_2(\mathbf{u}) + \xi^* L_{11}(\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}) \quad (20)$$

Further, the asymptotic expansion as defined by Equation (14) is modified to

$$\xi(\lambda - \lambda_c) = a\lambda_c \xi_c^2 + b\lambda_c \xi_c^3 - \lambda \xi^* + \dots \quad (21)$$

Including the effect of imperfections, Equation (14) is modified and can be written as

$$\left[1 - \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_c}\right] \xi + a\xi^2 + b\xi^3 = \left[\frac{\lambda}{\lambda_c}\right] \xi^* \quad (22)$$

Equation (22) can be seen as the reduced order model for the nonlinear static analysis.

3 Extension To Problems on Buckling under Dynamic Loading

In order to analyse problems on buckling under dynamic loading, such as dynamic buckling under step loading or parametric excitation under pulsating loading, inertial effects have to be taken into account. In this section, the extension of the perturbation approach for buckling under dynamic loading will be discussed. The procedure will be formulated within a multi-mode framework. Due to inertial forces the variational equation in Eq. (3) takes the form

$$\sigma \cdot \delta \varepsilon - \mathbf{f} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} + M(\ddot{\mathbf{u}}) \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (23)$$

where dots represent differentiation with respect to time and $M(\ddot{\mathbf{u}})$, which is linear in $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$, represents the

inertial loading. Here also the reciprocal relation as indicated in Eq. (6)

$$M(\mathbf{u}) \cdot \mathbf{v} = M(\mathbf{v}) \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (24)$$

holds. The dynamic loading is assumed to take the form $\mathbf{f} = \lambda F(t) \mathbf{f}_0$, where the time variation $F(t)$ is normalized so that its maximum value is unity. The dynamic displacements, strains, and stresses can be written as

$$\mathbf{u} = \lambda F(t) \mathbf{u}_0 + \mathbf{u}_i \xi_i(t) + \mathbf{u}_{ij} \xi_i(t) \xi_j(t) + \dots \quad (25)$$

$$\varepsilon = \lambda F(t) \varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_i \xi_i(t) + \varepsilon_{ij} \xi_i(t) \xi_j(t) + \dots \quad (26)$$

$$\sigma = \lambda F(t) \sigma_0 + \sigma_i \xi_i(t) + \sigma_{ij} \xi_i(t) \xi_j(t) + \dots \quad (27)$$

By repeating the same procedure as for the static case and neglecting the inertial forces associated with the pre-buckling displacements one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \xi_i''(t) + \left[1 - \frac{\lambda F(t)}{\lambda_I}\right] \xi_i(t) + a_{ijk} \xi_i(t) \xi_j(t) \xi_k(t) \\ + b_{ijkl} \xi_j(t) \xi_k(t) \xi_l(t) = \left[\frac{\lambda F(t)}{\lambda_I}\right] \xi_i^* \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where (') denotes differentiation with respect to time and where ω_I^2 is defined as

$$\omega_I^2 = \frac{\sigma_I \cdot \varepsilon_I}{M(\mathbf{u}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u}_I} \quad (29)$$

If \mathbf{u}_I happens to be a natural vibration mode then ω_I is its natural circular frequency otherwise ω_I^2 has an interpretation as a Rayleigh quotient for circular frequency squared based on the buckling mode \mathbf{u}_I . In the present implementation Eq. (28) is solved with a standard Runge-Kutta scheme of the 4th order.

In order to account for pre-buckling nonlinearity Eq. (29) is written as

$$\omega_I^2 = \frac{-\lambda_I \Delta_I}{M(\mathbf{u}_I) \cdot \mathbf{u}_I} \quad (30)$$

It can be noticed that the quantity $\sigma_I \cdot \varepsilon_I$ in Eq. (29) is replaced by $-\lambda_c \Delta_I$ in Eq. (30), with

$$\Delta_I = 2\sigma_I L_{11} \left(\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \lambda} \right)_c \cdot \mathbf{u}_I \right) + \left(\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \lambda} \right)_c \cdot L_2(\mathbf{u}_I) \quad (31)$$

where $(\)_c$, the quantities with subscript c, are pre-buckling quantities evaluated at the lowest bifurcation buckling load.

Finally, Eq. (28) is modified to

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{\omega_I} \right) \xi_I''(t) + \left[1 - \frac{\lambda F(t)}{\lambda_I} \right] \xi_I(t) + a_{Ijk} \xi_j(t) \xi_k(t) \\ + b_{ijkl} \xi_j(t) \xi_k(t) \xi_l(t) = \alpha_I \xi_I^* - \beta_I \left[1 - \frac{\lambda F(t)}{\lambda_I} \right] \xi_I^* \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where α_I and β_I are the so-called imperfection form factors [7]. In the case of a linear pre-buckling state both α_I and β_I are unity and Eq. (32) becomes identical to Eq. (28). Further, in the case of a nonlinear pre-buckling state the buckling analysis is carried out at a state close to the bifurcation buckling load, in contrast to the undeformed state considered in the case of a buckling analysis with a linear pre-buckling state.

On the basis of the previous discussion, the *reduction method* for buckling analysis under dynamic loading (such as dynamic buckling under step loading and parametric excitation under pulsating loading) proposed in the present work is described by the following step-by-step procedure, described here for the one-mode case:

- Establish the *reduced order model* for static buckling analysis, Equation (22):
 1. Computation of the pre-buckling state \mathbf{u}_0 .
 2. Computation of the buckling load λ_c and the corresponding buckling mode \mathbf{u}_1 .
 3. Computation of the second order mode \mathbf{u}_2 .
 4. Computation of the a and b coefficient.
- Establish the reduced order model for dynamic stability analysis, Equation (32), for a specific load case (such as a step load or a pulsating load).

- Carry out the *reduced analysis*:

1. Computation of the normalized mode amplitude $\xi(t)$ as function of time by solving Equation (28) by numerical time integration, for specified load amplitudes, increasing the amplitude of the applied load with small increments.
2. Recovering the displacement, stress, and strain by substituting the given loads and calculated amplitudes in Equation (25).
3. In the case of a dynamic buckling analysis: Identification of the dynamic buckling load level $\lambda = \lambda_d$, the level at which the maximum of $\xi(t)$ shows a sharp rise.

4 Finite Element Implementation

The finite element implementation of the perturbation approach discussed in the previous section has been done in the development environment of the general purpose finite element code DIANA using a layered, eight-node quadrilateral iso-parametric curved shell element, the CQ40L element. A description of this element is available in the DIANA manual. In order to use this element in the perturbation approach described, a modification of the element formulation is not required. However, it is necessary to construct \mathbf{B}_{NL} , the non-linear part of the strain-displacement matrix. In finite element notation the strain-displacement relation is given as

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{B}_L \mathbf{q} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{B}_{NL}(\mathbf{q}) \mathbf{q} \quad (38)$$

where \mathbf{B}_L and \mathbf{B}_{NL} , defined at each integration point, correspond to the L_1 functional and L_2 functional in Equation (1), and \mathbf{q} is the vector of nodal displacements at each element corresponding to the displacement field \mathbf{u} from the functional notation. In a similar way $L_{11}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ is translated to finite element notation as $\mathbf{B}_{NL}(\mathbf{q}_1) \mathbf{q}_2$, where the nodal displacement vectors \mathbf{q}_1 and \mathbf{q}_2 correspond to the displacement fields \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} in the functional

notation, respectively. In the following, we will discuss the finite element implementation briefly. Details of the implementation are available in earlier work of the present authors [7].

The static pre-buckling state \mathbf{q}_0 is obtained from a linear static analysis,

$$\mathbf{K}_0 \mathbf{q}_0 = \mathbf{f}_0 \quad (39)$$

where \mathbf{K}_0 is the global stiffness matrix at the undeformed state of the structure.

The buckling problem, in functional notation given by Equations (10), (11), and (12), corresponds to the following eigenvalue problem,

$$[\mathbf{K}_0 + \lambda_c \mathbf{K}_G] \mathbf{q}_1 = 0 \quad (40)$$

where \mathbf{K}_G is the geometric stiffness matrix. Solution of Equation (40) gives the lowest bifurcation buckling load λ_c and the corresponding buckling mode \mathbf{q}_1 .

The translation to finite element notation of the second order state problem, in functional notation represented by Equations (15), (16), and (17) gives

$$[\mathbf{K}_0 + \phi \lambda_c \mathbf{K}_G] \mathbf{q}_2 = \mathbf{g} \quad (41)$$

while the orthogonality constraint given by Equation (18) translates to

$$\mathbf{q}_1^T \mathbf{K}_G \mathbf{q}_2 = 0 \quad (42)$$

In Equation (41) the right-hand side force vector \mathbf{g} is given by

$$\mathbf{g} = -\frac{1}{2} \left[\mathbf{B}_L^T \mathbf{H} \mathbf{B}_{NL}(\mathbf{q}_1) \mathbf{q}_1 + 2 \mathbf{B}_{NL}^T(\mathbf{q}_1) \mathbf{H} \mathbf{B}_L \mathbf{q}_1 \right] \quad (43)$$

and ϕ is a factor such that $\phi \approx 1$, but $\phi < 1$. Usually $\phi = 0.99$ is applied, if $\phi = 1$ then Equation (41) becomes singular and cannot be solved. When pre-buckling nonlinearity is considered [7], Equations (41) and (42) include additional terms.

The b coefficient is obtained from Equation (19) by computing the post-buckling stresses and strains at each integration point, and summing them up over all the elements in the structure.

5 Results and Discussion

In this section, results of the reduction method are presented for a thin-walled structure under dynamic compressive loading. Results of the reduced order model for post-buckling analysis of a stiffened composite panel under axial step loading, based on a static buckling mode obtained using a nonlinear pre-buckling state analysis, are shown. The response of the structure in the reduced model is computed by numerically solving the reduced Equation (28) by a standard initial value solver. The buckling mode obtained from the bifurcation buckling analysis is normalized such that the maximum out-of-plane displacement is equal to the panel skin thickness.

A stiffened curved CFRP panel is considered. The skin of the panel has a cylindrical shape, which is 1/6 th of a full circular cylinder, i.e. creates an angle of 60° at the cylinder axis. The skin is stiffened by 6 equally spaced stringers. In the static analysis, this panel is axially compressed until collapse. This industrial benchmark was thoroughly studied earlier within a GARTEUR-SM (Group for Aeronautical Research and Technology in Europe - Structures and Materials) project using several finite element codes [8]. The modeling of the panel has been done in a similar way as was done by Samtech using SAMCEF (Fig. 1). The material and geometric properties of the panel are given in Tables 1 and 2.

In the static reduced order analysis, pre-buckling nonlinearity is considered. Results have been compared with full model nonlinear static analysis. The results of the static analysis (Fig. 2) form the basis of the dynamic analysis of the panel.

E_{11} [GPa]	141
E_{22} [GPa]	11
G_{12} [GPa]	6.29
G_{13} [GPa]	6.29
G_{23} [GPa]	4.29
ν_{12}	0.3
ρ [kg/mm ³]	1.6×10^{-6}

Table 1: Material properties of each ply of the curved CFRP panel.

Panel length	$l=800 \text{ mm}$
Free length (buckling length)	$l_f=620 \text{ mm}$
Radius (originally)	$r=400 \text{ mm}$
Number of stringers	$n=6$
Distance stringer to stringer	$d=a/6$
Distance stringer to longitudinal edge	$e=d/2$
Laminate set-up of skin	$[90,+45,-45,0]_S$
Laminate set-up of stringers	Blade: $[(+45,-45)_3,0_6]_S$ Foot: see [8]
Ply thickness	$t=0.125 \text{ mm}$
Stringer height	$h=14 \text{ mm}$
Stringer width	$f=37.9 \text{ mm}$

Table 2: Geometric properties of the curved CFRP panel.

In the dynamic analysis, the case of post-buckling under axial step loading has been investigated. The dynamic response under step loading, $F(t)=u_H(t)$, where u_H is the unit step function, of the imperfect structure has been evaluated using the reduced order model described by Equation (28). In the present work, a single mode study has been performed. The imperfection used in the analysis has the shape of the first buckling mode.

Characteristic analysis results will be presented. Fig. 3 shows the time history of the modal response calculated with the reduced order model for a moderate dynamic step load level of 20% of the static bifurcation buckling load, $\lambda=0.2\lambda_C$. The response is shown for two imperfection amplitudes, of 1% and 10% of the skin thickness, respectively.

Implicit dynamic finite element calculations have been carried out with ABAQUS. In Fig. 4 the results of the full model finite analysis under axial step loading is depicted. For the full model analysis, the out of plane displacement of a typical node of the skin, in the middle of a bay between two stringers where in the static analysis a buckle occurs, is plotted as a function of time. For this node, it can be seen that there is, also for a small imperfection of 1% of the skin thickness, a measurable contribution in the out-of-plane dynamic response. It should be noted that in the reduced order model analysis the

dynamic fundamental state response and the modal response are separately treated. In the finite element calculations a slight amount of damping was included, reducing the amplitude level of the response to a certain extent.

Although in the initial phase of the response the frequency characteristic of the reduced order model shows some resemblance to the frequency characteristic of the full model, the complexity of the behavior caused by the dynamic fundamental state response and by the participation of several modes and their interaction, the main characteristics of the response are not captured by the one-mode reduced order model. The contribution of several modes and the interactions between these modes has a significant effect on the response. In this case, the use of the multi-mode capability of the reduced order model is required in order to improve the response predictions of the reduced order model.

6 Concluding remarks

A perturbation approach has been used as the basis of a reduction method for the finite element buckling and post-buckling analysis of general thin-walled structures under dynamic loading. The formulation of a multi-mode reduced order model was presented. The implementation has been done within a general purpose finite element code.

In principle, a main advantage of the reduced order approach presented lies in the possibility of obtaining a quick evaluation of the structural response characteristics. Instead of carrying out a transient analysis with a (large) Finite Element model, one solves a set of ordinary differential equations through numerical time integration. Typical results for a single-mode buckling analysis under dynamic loading were shown for the complicated case of a composite stiffened panel under dynamic loading. The use of the multi-mode capability of the reduced order model is required in order to improve the response predictions of the model in situations, where several modes and their interactions play an important role. Earlier investigations on the post-buckling behavior of structures [9] have shown that the complicated behavior of large stiffened panels can in the static case be satisfactorily described by a multi-mode reduced order approach.

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Fig.1. Finite Element discretization of stiffened CFRP panel.

Fig. 2. Reduced order modeling for post-buckling analysis: Post-buckling deformation patterns corresponding to reduced order model analysis and full model Finite Element analysis of CFRP panel.

Fig.3. One-mode reduced order model response of CFRP panel: Modal response at dynamic step load level $\lambda=0.2\lambda_C$, with imperfections in the shape of the first buckling mode, 0.01% and 0.1% of the skin thickness.

Fig.4. Full Finite Element model response of CFRP panel: Typical nodal point response at dynamic step load level $\lambda=0.2\lambda_C$, with imperfections in the shape of the first buckling mode, 0.01% and 0.1% of the skin thickness.